

UV-accelerated weathering chamber for low-temperature material degradation: technical specifications

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Figure 1: Overall view of the UV chamber.

1 Introduction

This UV chamber is designed to irradiate materials to simulate their accelerated degradation using high surface power light (several hundred W/m^2) at low temperatures (around 20°C). A study conducted by a team from the University of Le Mans (IMMM Mixed research Unite, Le Mans, France) using an incandescent UV lamp served as the basis for defining its characteristics.

2 Operating instructions

The typical use of this chamber is at half-power continuously for 10 to 60 days.

Ultraviolet radiation is invisible to the eye but not without danger, so it is recommended to wear dedicated protective glasses. The surface of the chamber can reach a relatively high temperature, so be careful of the risk of burn.

A safety feature prevents UV lamps from operating with the door open. To turn on the UV lamps, close the door and press the "ON" button. In the event of a momentary power outage, the chamber does not restart automatically; "ON" button must be pressed again.

The fans and electrical outlets inside the chamber operate without the door safety feature.

The chamber is relatively heavy; to move it, do not carry it by the electrical panel !

3 Physical and electrical characteristics

- Dimensions (LxPxH) : $\sim 630 \times 530 \times 445\text{mm}$
- Usable dimensions (LxPxH) : $\sim 430 \times 400 \times 240\text{mm}$
- Weight : $\sim 21\text{kg}$
- Main power supply: $100 - 300\text{V}_{AC}$, $47 - 63\text{Hz}$, 1A
- Fuse: $5 \times 20\text{mm}$, 4 A time-delay

4 LED panels

The LED panels were custom-made by Agrotek with the following characteristics:

- Mix U.V. : ratio UVA:UVB = $79 : 21\%$
- UV-A, SMD 3030, 0.8W , quantity 100, relative spectral distribution : 365nm [360nm - 370nm], manufacturer LEDESTAR, reference : LDR-3030TTAV365-V0V A0H0
- UV-B, SMD 3535, 1.2W , quantity 25, relative spectral distribution : 310nm [290nm - 350nm], manufacturer LEDESTAR, reference : LDR-3535CNZV310-M0
- Driver with power dimming in 20% increments, MeanWell XLG-150-H-AB

Figure 2: Distribution of UV-A and UV-B LEDs on the panels. Blue squares represent the UV-A LEDs, while purple squares represent the UV-B LEDs.

Measurements carried out on a driver panel assembly at ambient temperature *:

Pos.	$R_{add}(k\Omega)$	$P_{line}(W)$	$V_{led}(V)$	$I_{led}(A)$	$P_{led}(W)$	$\eta_{elec}(\%)$	$T_{in}(^{\circ}C)$	$T_{rise}(^{\circ}C)$
0	0	0	4,1	0,000	0	-	20,8	0
20	47	13,4	37,6	0,325	12,22	91,19	23,9	3,1
40	138	45,0	39,1	1,060	41,45	92,10	30,2	9,4
60	220	74,4	39,9	1,713	68,35	91,87	35,3	14,5
80	280	96,1	40,4	2,197	88,76	92,36	38,6	17,8
100	infini	122,0	40,8	2,764	112,775	92,44	42,9	22,1

* : *Electrical values were measured for one LED panel coupled with one driver. For the power corresponding to the chamber, multiply the values by two. Temperatures were measured while both panels operate simultaneously.*

5 Power density

The average power density (PD) have been measured for the two most frequently used positions 20% and 40% that won't damage LED panels over long periods of use. The device used to make measurements on the chamber platform was the PM400 optical power and energy meter console (Thorlabs) equipped with the thermal power sensor head S401C (surface absorber, 0.19 - 20 μm , 10 μW - 1 W, 10 mm).

Pos.	PD_{UV-A} (W/m ²)		PD_{UV-B} (W/m ²)	
	Average	CI 95%	Average	CI 95%
20	309	[252 - 366]	91.17	[47.4 - 136]
40	894	[748 - 1040]	281	[199 - 363]

6 Materials

The chamber is primarily made of plywood panels painted on the exterior and covered with aluminum sheets on the interior. The electrical enclosure is made of polycarbonate.

7 Electrical diagram

Figure 3: Electrical diagram of the UV chamber.

8 References

This up-to-date notice can be downloaded at the following address:

https://github.com/EdgarDusacre/Plasfito_public/blob/main/UV_chamber/Dusacre_et_al_2024.pdf

Agrotek SAS

25 rue General Ferrié

38100 Grenoble, FRANCE

<https://www.agrotek.fr>

Middle Power LED
3030

302G UVA Series
Purple

Features & Benefits

- 1.0 W class middle power LED
- Mold resin for high reliability
- Standard form factor for design flexibility (3.0 × 3.0 mm)
- Radiant Efficiency @300mA: typ.31.1%

1. Characteristics

a) Absolute Maximum Rating

Item	Symbol	Rating	Unit	Condition
Ambient / Operating Temperature	T_a	-40 ~ +105	°C	-
Storage Temperature	T_{stg}	-40 ~ +105	°C	-
LED Junction Temperature	T_j	125	°C	-
Forward Current	I_F	300	mA	-
Pulse Forward Current	I_{FP}	600	mA	Duty 1/10, pulse width 10ms
Assembly Process Temperature	-	260 <10	°C s	-
ESD (HBM)	-	0.5	kV	-

b) Electro-optical Characteristics ($I_F = 300 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$)

Item	Unit	Rank	Min.	Typ.	Max.
Forward Voltage (V_F)	V	V0	3.2	3.4	3.6
Reverse Current (I_R) (@VR=5V)	uA		-	-	1
Peak wavelength (λ_p)	nm	VA0	365	-	375
Radiant Power	mW	H0	280	300	350
Electrical thermal resistance junction/ solderpoint with efficiency ($R_{thJS \text{ elec.}}$) $\eta_e = 31.1\%$	°C/W		-	13	-
Beam Angle	°		-	120	-

Note:

Ledstar maintains measurement tolerance of: Radiant Power = $\pm 7\%$, forward voltage = $\pm 0.1 \text{ V}$, Wavelength = $\pm 2 \text{ nm}$

2. Product Code Information

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21		
L	D	R	-	3	0	3	0	T	T	A	V	3	6	5	-	V	0	V	A	0	H	0

Digit	PKG Information	Code	Specification
1 2 3	Ledstar Package Middle Power	LDR	
4 5 6 7	Package Model and Size	3030	3.0 x 3.0 x 0.65mm
8	Product Category	T	Top View
9	Bractek Type	T	PCT & Cu
10	Version	A	
11	Color	V	Violet
12 13 14	Wavelength Typical (nm)	365	365~375
15 16	Forward Voltage (V)	V0	3.2~3.6 Bin Code: H0 3.2~3.4 H1 3.2~3.3 H2 3.3~3.4 J0 3.4~3.6 J1 3.4~3.5 J2 3.5~3.6
17 18 19	Peak Wavelength (nm)	VA0 VA1 VA2	VA1 VA2 365~370 370~375
20 21	Radiant Power (mW)	H0 HY HZ	HY HZ 280~300 300~350

a) Voltage Bins ($I_F = 300 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Voltage Rank	Voltage Bin	Voltage Range (V)
LDR-3030TTAV365-V0VA0H0	V0	H1	3.2 ~ 3.3
		H2	3.3 ~ 3.4
		J1	3.4 ~ 3.5
		J2	3.5 ~ 3.6

b) Wavelength Bins ($I_F = 300 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Wavelength Rank	Wavelength Bin	Wavelength Range (nm)
LDR-3030TTAV365-V0VA0H0	VA0	VA1	365 ~ 370
		VA2	370 ~ 375

c) Radiant Power Bins ($I_F = 300 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Power Rank	Power Bin	Power Range (mW)
LDR-3030TTAV365-V0VA0H0	H0	HY	280 ~ 300
		HZ	300 ~ 350

3. Typical Characteristics Graphs

a) Spectrum Distribution ($I_f = 300\text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$)

b) Temperature Characteristics ($I_f = 300\text{ mA}$)

c) Forward Current Characteristics ($T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$)

d) Color Shift Characteristics, $T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$

e) Derating Curve

f) Beam Angle Characteristics ($T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $I_F = 300\text{ mA}$)

Middle Power LED
3535

351W UVB Series
Ultraviolet

For Disinfect Lighting

Features & Benefits

- 0.8 W class middle power LED
- Mold resin for high reliability
- Standard form factor for design flexibility (3.5 × 3.5 mm)

1. Characteristics

a) Absolute Maximum Rating

Item	Symbol	Rating	Unit	Condition
Ambient / Operating Temperature	T_a	-40 ~ +60	°C	-
Storage Temperature	T_{stg}	-40 ~ +60	°C	-
LED Junction Temperature	T_j	85	°C	-
Forward Current	I_F	100	mA	-
Pulse Forward Current	I_{FP}	200	mA	Duty 1/10, pulse width 10ms
Assembly Process Temperature	-	220 <10	°C s	-
ESD (HBM)	-	6	kV	-

b) Electro-optical Characteristics ($I_F = 40 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ °C}$)

Item	Unit	Rank	Min.	Typ.	Max.
Forward Voltage (V_F)	V	M0	5.0	-	7.0
Peak wavelength (λ_p)	nm	VB0	305	-	315
Radiant Power (Φ_e)	mW	L0	3	-	5
Thermal Resistance (junction to solder point)	°C/W		-	5	-
Beam Angle	°		-	120	-

Note:

Ledstar maintains measurement tolerance of: forward voltage = $\pm 0.1 \text{ V}$, Radiant Power = $\pm 5 \%$, Wavelength = $\pm 2 \text{ nm}$

2. Product Code Information

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21		
L	D	R	-	3	5	3	5	C	N	Z	V	3	1	0	-	M	0	V	B	0	L	0

Digit	PKG Information	Code	Specification
1 2 3	Ledstar Package Middle Power	LDR	
4 5 6 7	Package Model and Size	3535	3.5 x 3.5 x 1.47mm
8	Product Category	C	Ceramics
9	Bractek Type	N	AlN
10	Version	Z	With Zener
11	Color	V	Violet
12 13 14	Wavelength Typical (nm)	310	305~315
15 16	Forward Voltage (V)	M0	5.0~7.0
17 18 19	Peak Wavelength (nm)	VC0 VB1 VB2	VB1 VB2 305~310 310~315
20 21	Radiant Power (mW)	LA LC LD	LC LD 3.0~4.0 4.0~5.0

a) Voltage Bins ($I_F = 40 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Voltage Rank	Voltage Range (V)
LDR-3535CNZV310-M0VB0L0	M0	5.0 ~ 5.5
		5.5 ~ 6.0
		6.0 ~ 6.5
		6.5 ~ 7.0

b) Wavelength Bins ($I_F = 40 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Wavelength Rank	Wavelength Bin	Wavelength Range (nm)
LDR-3535CNZV310-M0VB0L0	VB0	VB1	305 ~ 310
		VB2	310 ~ 315

c) Radiant Power Bins ($I_F = 40 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

Product Code	Power Rank	Power Bin	Power Range (mW)
LDR-3535CNZV310-M0VB0L0	L0	LC	3 ~ 4
		LD	4 ~ 5

3. Typical Characteristics Graphs

a) Spectrum Distribution ($I_f = 40 \text{ mA}$, $T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$)

WLP:305-315nm

b) Temperature Characteristics ($I_f = 40 \text{ mA}$)

c) Forward Current Characteristics ($T_s = 25^\circ\text{C}$)

d) Derating Curve

e) Beam Angle Characteristics ($T_j = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $I_f = 40\text{ mA}$)

